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An Analysis on the Relationship between Art and Science and Technology on the Twenty-eight Constellation of Yuhuang Temple in Zezhou

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ABSTRACT

In Jincheng, the Zezhou Yuhuang temple is a ritual sacrificial structure. Its plane layout and architectural form reflect Chinese traditional religious beliefs' etiquette and sacrificial practices. In terms of decorative statues, the portraits of the Yuan Dynasty's 28th constellation are the most classic. Furthermore, the colored glaze art of the Yuhuang temple exemplifies the organic relationship between art, science, and technology. The religious structures in southeastern Shanxi represented by Zezhou Yuhuang temple have realized the unity of colored glaze art, science, and technology from this perspective. The colored glaze shape of the twenty-eight nights burned on the main ridge of the Yuhuang temple in the Jin Dynasty is of great artistic value, and the character color and artistic features of its costumes are astounding. The 28th clay sculpture at the Yuhuang temple's main ridge is mainly reflected in its production background, the increase of types, the enrichment of content, the preservation of color, and so on in art, science, and technology.

Keywords

Zezhou Yuhuang temple; Art of Colored Glaze; Art and Technology

1. Introduction

The history of glazed art development in Shanxi Province's southeast is relatively long. Colored glaze is widely used in various buildings, particularly religious buildings, and is not only used as a decoration. Currently, many of the religious buildings leftover from Shanxi Province's southeast have adopted colored glaze production technology. Even though these colored glaze components have been around for thousands of years, they continue to be valued for their exquisite technology, making the building itself a work of art.

The Yuhuang temple in Zezhou, Jincheng, Shanxi Province, is the most representative of these religious structures.

2. The development of colored glaze art in religious architecture in Southeast Shanxi

China has a long history of producing colored glaze. According to some documents, China could produce colored glaze during the Western Zhou Dynasty. However, due to limited production technology at the time, colored glaze manufacturing was still in its early stage, and the type of ware was simple. China's colored glaze production and manufacturing technology greatly improved during the Spring and Autumn time of the Warring States period, and various types of utensils appeared, which had become an ornament relished by the nobility at the time. [1] Colored glaze has been used not only for decoration but also in religious and other architectural fields in China since the Han Dynasty and has left an important mark on the country's architectural history.

Shanxi Province is a major-colored glaze-producing region in China, particularly in the province's southeast. The colored glaze ware produced is incredibly beautiful. The glazed ware types in the southern region of Shanxi have a variety of forms, and the production technology is very exquisite, which plays an important role in the application of glazed art in later buildings, according to the cultural relics that have been unearthed at this time.

There were two-color glaze and multi-color glaze in addition to monochrome glaze during the Han Dynasty. The glazed art has become more mature over time, laying the groundwork for the development of glazed architecture in Shanxi, particularly the emergence and use of tricolor glaze after the Tang Dynasty.

In the southeast of Shanxi Province, the use of glazed art in architecture dates to the Northern Wei Dynasty. Colored glaze was used in the construction of palaces in the southeast of Shanxi Province during the Northern Wei Dynasty, and it absorbed relevant nutrients from the western regions' firing technology, allowing it to play a larger role. Colored glaze has evolved into not only an art form but also an important architectural technology. It is widely used as a decorative element in buildings. [2]

A breakthrough in glazed technology occurred in the southeast of Shanxi during the Sui and Tang Dynasties, primarily in the use of the Tang Tricolor. Figure figurines and animal figurines made with colored glaze technology have a lot of detail, are different in shape, and have a lot of colors. Their glaze colors come in a wide range of hues. There have been Buddha statues made with colored glaze technology in ancient temples near Jiexiu City, Shanxi Province, as an example of an attempt to effectively use colored glaze technology in ancient temples and other religious buildings. Furthermore, the scale of applying colored glaze technology to the field of architecture in the southeast of Shanxi Province was larger than before during the Sui and Tang Dynasties. Many of the Sui and Tang Dynasties' buildings in Shanxi use colored glaze production technology, such as colored glaze kissing animals, colored glaze tiles, and so on.

There was a new climax in the development of glazed technology in the southeast of Shanxi Province during the Song Dynasty and the Liao and Jin Dynasties. During that time, ancient China experienced a period of rapid development in the field of architecture, with particular attention paid to how to decorate architecture and use of color. The colored glaze construction objects in the building, as well as the colored glaze roof filled with the building's top, emphasize the building's high unity of exterior and color, emphasizing the building's artistic effect. During this time, colored glaze and architecture were seamlessly combined. Aside from the use of colored glaze for building components, some colored glaze decorations on buildings have appeared one after the other. The use of colored glaze technology for architectural decoration is relatively common in religious buildings in Shanxi Province's southeast, and there are many existing relics in Shanxi, such as the Yuhuang temple in Zezhou, Jincheng, Shanxi Province, which can be found in almost every region of Shanxi Province.

The Yuan Dynasty brought an end to the Song and Jin Dynasties' divide, creating a favorable environment for the development of the handicraft industry and other industries. [3] In the southeast of Shanxi Province, the glazing industry has reached a prosperous stage in its development. In comparison to the previous period, both raw materials and glaze color have advanced significantly in the colored glaze-making process. A series of new glazed components, for example, has appeared in the shape; there are rich color patterns on the glaze color, which enhance the beauty of the building. There are still glazed building components in the Yuan Dynasty, especially in religious buildings, as evidenced by some existing temples in southeastern Shanxi. During that time, glazed buildings were frequently used as decorative elements.

The glazing industry in Southeast Shanxi reached a new level of development during the Ming and Qing dynasties, with scale, distribution, and technology that had never been seen before. During this time, the glazed objects used in religious buildings became more exquisite, and flexible and diverse images, such as positive kisses and animal pieces, appeared, all of which were very fine glazed works of art. The emerald, blue technology and emerald, green technology in the color glaze is more shaped for glazed products in the Ming and Qing Dynasties, and the color of glazed products is also very skilled. A color system, for example, can be divided into different types of colors. The themes of colored glaze products in the southeast of Shanxi during the Ming and Qing Dynasties were diverse, especially in the Qing Dynasty, when its colored glaze products displayed obvious secularization characteristics, which contained people's good wishes.

3. Plane layout and spatial form of Yuhuang temple in Zezhou

In Jincheng, Shanxi Province, the Zezhou Yuhuang temple is located on the Beigang of Fucheng village, 12 kilometers northeast of Jincheng City. It was founded in the Northern Song Dynasty's ninth year of Xining (1076), rebuilt in the seventh year of Jintaihe (1207), and a mountain gate was built in the fifteenth year of Yuan Zhizheng (1355). It is a collection of magnificent Taoist structures. The temple is surrounded by towering cypress trees and a plethora of flowers and trees, particularly the 183 Yuan Dynasty colored

sculptures. There are more than 120 constellations in this Taoist complex, which is divided into four courtyards. The Yuhuang temple is in the north and south of the city. The temple's central axes are East-West. The newly constructed gate is located on the east central axis. The kitchen, office, and guest room are located on the east side. Finally, in the East and West, there are three Guanwang halls. The temple's main buildings are aligned along the West axis, the two compartments are symmetrical, and the temple yard's terrain gradually rises from front to back.

According to the existing inscriptions in the temple, the Yuhuang temple has been rebuilt and maintained five times since its construction. The temple's appearance will change to some extent with each reconstruction. The annals of creating the temple gate screen provide important information about the temple's initial construction: during the Sui Dynasty, the people of Zezhou built a temple locally. There were only three rooms at the time, and the "Sanqing" statues were enshrined. This temple, however, is not the Yuhuang temple that we see today, nor was it expanded in the same way as the "Sanqing Temple," but was rebuilt nearby. The Song Dynasty should have built the Yuhuang temple. Although it has been rebuilt many times since then, the overall style of the temple still reflects the Song Dynasty's architectural style, and there has been no significant change in its development. The rafters of the Yuhuang temple were damaged during the Jin Dynasty because they had not been repaired for many years. As a result, the residents of the area had raised funds specifically to repair it and restore its former architectural appearance. War damaged the Yuhuang temple during the Yuan Dynasty, and the damage was relatively severe. The temple's main hall was not damaged during the war, but its East and West halls were. The Yuhuang temple was later repaired, especially the East and West side halls, and the twenty-eight Xingxiu statues in the temple were repaired in all aspects, according to the stele of the Yuhuang Emperor's palace. The Yuhuang temple was also repaired several times during the Ming and Qing dynasties, but the scale of the repairs remained minor, and the overall structure of the temple did not change significantly. The main pattern of Yuhuang temple today is based on the basic style and features that it had when it was rebuilt during the Yuan Dynasty.

The first entrance to the courtyard is the location of the specific distribution. The courtyard wall door is on the front. According to the terrain, the courtyard is divided into upper and lower platforms. The lower platform's east and west sides are wing rooms, the upper platform's east and west sides are Beiting (Qing Dynasty buildings), and the back is Toudao Mountain Gate (buildings in the Ming Dynasty).

The upper and lower platforms make up the terrain of the second hospital. Two-story hard mountain buildings line both sides of the lower platform. On the east side of the upper platform is Wenchang hall, and on the west side is the throat temple, both of which are Qing Dynasty structures. The mountain has two mountain gates in the middle, which are a Yuan Dynasty legacy.

The courtyard area is small at the third entrance, so the treatment method of high and low complements with the terrain is used. The main hall and the rear hall are built on the same level. In front of the main hall,

there is a platform that is 33.5 cm lower than the main hall platform and 45 cm higher than the second Mountain Gate platform. In the middle of the courtyard, there are moderately tall corridors and stone steps with a well-coordinated layout. The six-plaque hall, the bell tower in the East, the underground Tibetan Hall in the West, and the drum tower in the West make up the East rear Hall of Erdaoshan Gate. The Wudao hall is in the south section of the East chamber, while the forbidden king hall is in the north section. A high media temple, the west chamber is. The main hall, the Tang Hall, a Jin Dynasty structure, is located on the upper level of the courtyard. The Dongyue hall is on the east side of the main hall, and the three king's hall is on the west.

The Yuhuang temple's main courtyard is the temple's fourth entrance. Taiwei hall, silkworm temple, Guanwang hall, horse corridor, and thirteen Yao star hall make up the East corridor constellation, which runs from south to north. There are a total of 11 East corridor constellations. The twenty-eight Susu hall is located to the south of the west corridor constellation, while the twelve Chen Hall is located to the north. A small hall was built at the end of the East and West verandas, with Fengbo hall in the East and Yushi hall in the West. The Yuhuang Emperor Hall is to the north of the courtyard, with the rear hall on both sides, the three-yuan hall to the east, and the four holy halls to the west. The offering hall is in front of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall on the central axis. This is a Taoist architectural complex that has been well preserved.

The Yuhuang temple has an erdaoshan gate, which is a typical Yuan Dynasty structure. This structure is located behind the Yuhuang temple's second entrance and serves as a link between the past and the future. As a result, the craftsmen have unique design wisdom, and the plate gate is displaced in the middle column, allowing a building to serve as a door, corridor, and hall all at once. The so-called gate is the erdaoshan gate; the so-called corridors are the front and back corridors; and the so-called temple, which is located on the axis, is shaped like a temple. The multiple functions of a structure demonstrate ancient craftsmen's brilliant design ideas. With a suspended mountain roof, Erdaoshan has three wide doors and two deep doors. It is constructed on a high stone platform with nine vertical belt steps set in front of it, and the platform is pressed with stones. The front porch is made of stone square columns with plastered four corners, which is a common technique in Shanxi Province's southeast. The back porch is made up of round wooden columns, and the gate is placed between four central columns in the hall. The door is a plate door with a straightforward design and system.

The East rear hall is a three-wall hall with two rooms, a front porch, and four paved capitals and a single high, hanging on the top of the mountain. The West Rear Hall is a four-temple structure with three rooms, a front porch, a hard peak, and four paved capitals. The main hall and the two-rear hall are both Yuan Dynasty structures. In the hall, there are colored sculptures from the Song Dynasty that have been preserved.

From south to north, there are 11 East corridor verandas with front porches that run the length of the mountain. Taiwei hall, silkworm temple, Guanwang hall, stables, and thirteen Yao star hall are the names of the buildings. On the back wall of the Guanwang Palace's stables, a door is opened, a small courtyard is built,

and three rooms of the Guanwang Palace are built (see above). It contains several statues that, in terms of style, are Ming Dynasty works. The thirteen Yao star hall's roof is slightly higher. Each hall has colored sculptures, including works from the Song Dynasty as well as the Ming and Qing Dynasties. There are 11 rooms in total on the west corridor veranda. The Su Hall is in the south, while the Chen Hall is in the north. The East veranda has the same structure as the West veranda. Experts have identified twenty-eight sun-colored sculptures in the hall of twenty-eight suns as the work of Liu Luan, a great sculptor of the Yuan Dynasty. There are twelve zodiac personalized colored sculptures in the hall of twelve suns, all of which are Song Dynasty works. Fengbo hall in the East and Yushi hall in the West are both small rooms at the end of the East and West verandas.

4. The art and craft of glaze in Zezhou Yuhuang temple

Overall, the glaze of the Zezhou Yuhuang temple can be divided into two types: glazed tiles and glazed ornaments. The former refers to all types of glazed tiles, such as tube and ridge tiles, while the latter refers to glazed components made of glazed materials, such as immortal. Most of the colored glazes in the temple are constructed around the central axis and are primarily three colors: yellow, green, and peacock blue.

In Zezhou's Yuhuang temple, there are many colored glazes works of art. The 28-clay sculpture ridge in the Yuhuang Emperor Hall, the main hall, is the most famous. Furthermore, the peacock blue colored glaze products in Toudao Mountain Gate are decorative and colorful. The colored glaze art in Zezhou's Yuhuang temple has been shining for thousands of years. Its color has faded over time, but it is still vibrant. The decorative modeling and manufacturing techniques of the colored glaze still reflect the unique aesthetic taste of the time.

4.1 Process of Burning Colored glaze in Zezhou Yuhuang temple

As can be seen from the chart above, the southeastern region has a long history of glazing development. In the production of glazing, Jincheng's use of glazing is the most well-known. The buildings of each period have pieces of glazed material, according to the general situation of the ancient buildings left behind today. [4] The Yuhuang temple of Zezhou, however, is the most distinctive of these structures. The colored glaze industry in the southeastern part of the province was heavily molded and developed into an intensive industry with a very clear division of labor and a large scale at the start of the Ming Dynasty. We are in a very strong position in the country in terms of scale, operation skills, and the number of people employed in the colored glaze industry.

The production of glazing in south-eastern Shanxi can be traced back to the Song Dynasty, according to existing physical materials and related documents, and some glazing industry families have emerged. The production of glazed colored glaze in Shanxi's south-eastern area was already very high during the Ming Dynasty. Glazed colored glaze was produced not only in a variety of types, but also with very fine

manufacturing technology and a unique style, with vibrant colors, during the relatively heyday of development. The glazed elements on the building have a vibrant shape, with numerous decorative shapes of uniform models.

The technology of their production process, which includes more scientific technical methods, can be seen in all kinds of glazing products and components in the Yuhuang Temple of Zezhou. The result is a significant improvement in glazing raw materials, improved control of glazing product calcining temperatures, raising enamel technology, and porcelain kiln burning technology. First, when the glaze is applied, the required raw material is changed to glaze ash, which is improved to increase the content of potassium oxide in the glaze. [5] Second, during the burning process, the thickness of the glaze layer and its temperature should be accurately judged, so that more new glaze products can be made, for example. Nonetheless, the way of burning and the way of "lighting" were used in the manufacture of glazed colored glaze at the time in the Yuhuang temple of Zezhou. Furthermore, because the coal resources in Zezhou, Jincheng, are abundant and sufficient, the Chinese porcelain products that use the relevant coal technology in the Yuhuang Temple of Zezhou have been used to burn the glaze.

4.2 Technical characteristics of glaze in Zezhou Yuhuang temple

Most of the colored glaze techniques used in the Yuhuang temple in Zezhou are related to the art of kneading flowers, making the building's color glaze more ornamental. The roof of the temple's Yuhuang Emperor Hall is made of yellow glazed tiles, and the trimming is made of green glazed tiles, giving the temple a solemn appearance. The roof color glaze of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall was made during the Jin Dynasty, according to the inscriptions on the stele. Furthermore, other colored glaze components in the temple do not list a specific manufacturer or date of manufacture but based on the exquisite quality of the temple's color glaze products and colored glaze production in eastern and southern Shanxi since the Song Dynasty, the temple's colored glaze making level was already at the forefront of society at the time.

Glazed tiles are also very exquisite artistic products in the Yuhuang temple in Zezhou glazed products. Glazed tiles have played an important role in Chinese architecture throughout history. Glazed tiles played an important role in architecture during the Qin and Han Dynasties. When it came to glazed tiles, Zezhou Yuhuang temple inherited and continued the Qin and Han Dynasties' glazed tile technology. It has a unique style based on absorbing its artistic connotation, as well as the characteristics of glazed production technology in Southeast Shanxi and the high level of glazed production at the time. The main colors of temple glazed tiles are yellow, travel color, and peacock blue, which can not only reflect the temple's solemnity, but also add artistic beauty to the architecture.

The Yuhuang temple in Zezhou, in addition to preserving Jin Dynasty glazed products, is also rich in glazed products from other periods. In the temple, the number of glazed products from the Ming Dynasty is particularly large. The Ming Dynasty's colored glaze production technology has advanced to a certain level

and realm, as evidenced by the temple's relics of Ming Dynasty colored glaze products. The temple's glazed ware and enamel ware are typical of the manufacturing process. Glazed ware glaze is primarily made of colored glaze products, with lead as a flux and some metal substances such as iron as colorants, before being scientifically mixed with quartz and fired. The clay is primarily used as the tire in porcelain ware, and the tread is formed by powder leaching to create patterns with line characteristics. The tread is then filled with characteristic bases to form different colors in the patterns, and it is then coated with glaze of various colors. Finally, it is fired in a kiln to create glazed products. The colored glaze production of Yuhuang temple in Zezhou has advanced technology, which focuses on colored glaze making technology in Southeast Shanxi and even Shanxi Province, representing the highest level of colored glaze production at the time, according to the Ming Dynasty's colored glaze making process.

5. Modeling characteristics of the colored glaze of the twenty-eight constellations on the main ridge of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall

5.1 A brief introduction to the image of the twenty-eight stars

The Yuhuang Emperor Hall is the focal point of Zezhou's Yuhuang temple. A colored glaze statue of twenty-eight constellations sits atop its main ridge. The twenty-eight constellations' records first appeared during the Warring States period. It dates to the Zhou Dynasty. The imperial court put Feng Xiang and Bao Zhang in charge of astronomy at the time. They divided the stars in the Zhou Dynasty's sky into three walls and twenty-eight constellations, each named. Later, previous dynasties' astronomical calendars were based on the preceding example, and were endowed with good and bad luck, resulting in the so-called Chinese astrology theory. Each of the twenty-eight constellations had a star in charge in the romance of the gods. During the Shang and Zhou dynasties' battle, all 28 stars perished in the ten thousand immortals' array. They were later given the title of star king of the twenty-eight constellations when Jiang Ziya became a God.

The 28-star constellations chosen by ancient Chinese astronomers to observe celestial phenomena and the movement of the sun, moon, and five stars in the sky, circling the sky on both sides of the ecliptic belt and the equatorial belt, are known as the twenty-eight constellations. Starting with the horn pointed by the handle of the Big Dipper, the twenty-eight constellations are arranged from east to west. In ancient China, their names, when combined with the three walls, became the standard for dividing the sky. The 28 stars were divided into four groups, each with seven stars, and the ancients imagined them to be various animal images. The "four elephants" are the stars in the east that are dragon-shaped, the stars in the west that are tiger-shaped, the stars in the south that are bird-shaped, and the stars in the north that are turtle and snake-shaped. It was combined with the five elements theory with the theory of five sides and five colors after the five elements theory emerged. The seven stars of the East are horn, Kang, surname, room, heart, tail, and dustpan, all of which belong to wood and are green in color. The seven Western Stars are Kui, Lou, stomach, ang, Bi, purple, and ginseng, because the west is golden and white. The South is associated with fire, and its color is red, so it is

known as the South's seven stars: ghost, willow, star, Zhang, wing, and rosefinch. The seven northern stars are named after the water and black nature of the north: Dou, Niu, Nu, Xu, danger, room, and wall. It's Xuanwu (Xuanwu is the intersection of turtle and snake). Black and Xuanwu). In the early Tang Dynasty, Yuan Tiangang, a five connoisseur, linked the twenty-eight constellations with 28 different animals, and added sun, moon, gold, wood, water, fire, and earth to each constellation's name. The constellation's name was changed from one word to three words, which were incorporated into the "four images" and colored, resulting in the following four organizations:

1. **Oriental Green Dragon:** JiaoMu Jiao, Kang Jinlong, Tu Raccoon, FangRi Rabbit, Xinyue Fox, Tail Fire Tiger, Jishui Leopard. It has a dragon-like shape and is blue in color.
2. **Northern basaltic:** Doumu Nuo, Niujinniu, Female Earth Bat, Virtual Day Mouse, Dangerous Moon Swallow, Room Fire Pig, Wall Water Transportation. It has a shape like turtle and snake and is black in color.
3. **Western White Tigers:** Kui Mu Wolf, Lou Jingou, Wei Tuxiong, Jingri Chicken, Bi YUEWU, Purple Fire Monkey and Shenshui Ape. It has a Tiger shape and is white in color.
4. **Southern Rosefinch:** Well Wood Stalk, Ghost Golden Sheep, Willow Soil Camphor, Xingri Horse, Zhang Yuelu, Winged Fire Snake and Water Worm. It has a bird-like shape and is red in color.

5.2 Yuhuang Emperor Hall Main Ridge Colored Glaze Twenty-eight Residential Figure Image

The "Jishui leopard" (picture) in 28su's colored glaze statue, for example, is a warrior image. He is enraged when he sees him wearing the incorrect armor; his expression is rough and exaggerated; he stares him down; his right hand clenches his fist and holds it high. The "Shenshui ape" (picture) with "water" in the colored glaze statue of twenty-eight nights is an image of a rich female official wearing a corolla, holding a wat board, wearing colored clothes, wrapped with colored ribbons on his arms, generous and decent, stepping on auspicious clouds, and an ape image climbing up along the colored ribbons on the right, dynamic, naturistic. The characters are given a strong sense of rhythm by the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eighth night, whether moving or static, with ups and downs. Reaching out and throwing feet appears to be a completely natural posture with no rigidity. The color ribbons wrapped between the arms of the "God kings" form a unique style on the main ridge of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall. It breaks the lengthy format of the main ridge of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall and destroys the rigid feeling of the rectangle. Among the many color glaze ridge decorations in the Yuhuang temple of Zezhou, the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eight constellations on the main ridge of the Yuhuang Emperor Hall are fine works of art. Their sculptures have a distinct style and personality. This collection of Jin Dynasty colored glaze sculptures exemplifies an innovative theme and a novel method of expression in the creation of religious colored glaze sculptures in ancient China. They are

"unique products" of Taoist figure statues that already exist. It has left valuable artifacts for the study of Taoist colored glaze statue culture and art.

5.3 Yuhuang Emperor Hall Main Ridge Colored Glaze Twenty-eight Residential Figure Costume

The main ridge of the Yuhuang Emperor's 28th constellation, which was fired in the Jin Dynasty and made by Li Daozhen, a dongyuanqing craftsman in Zezhou, is now in Jincheng Museum. In the Ming Dynasty, the main ridge of the temple on site is restored and copied. The Yuhuang Emperor Hall is the Yuhuang temple's main hall. The colored glaze ornaments on the constellation's main ridge are a statue of the star king of the twenty-eight constellations, not ordinary carvings. The ancients of our country sculpted the twenty-eight stars into immortals and related animals and carved them on ridge blocks, which were then painted with colored glaze and fired. The way the ridge blocks are arranged on the roof is so well-coordinated, demonstrating our forefathers' ingenuity. We can no longer see the complete twenty-eight nights after the restoration of Zhengji in the Ming Dynasty, but we can still clearly see the stars, men or women, literature, or martial arts, stepping on clouds, holding magic tools, surrounded by animals and animals, with various expressions, who are very responsible to guard over the Yuhuang Emperor, from the remaining rare ridge blocks. Although some of the colored glaze colors have mottled after 800 years of wind and rain erosion, most of them are still bright and shining. At the time, the level of birth and color burning was ideal.

Painting and sculpture had a big influence on the development of ancient Chinese traditional colored glaze art. Colored glaze plastic artists are making artistic creations under the influence of this artistic pursuit, and they have put a lot of effort into the "charm" of their works. The viewer was struck by the shape of the twenty-eight-star glazed ridge figure in the Yuhuang Emperor Hall. It uses a glazed technique that is related to the art of pinching flowers. The viewer gets the impression that the colored glaze statue art of the twenty-eight nights in the Yuhuang Emperor Hall has both individuality and commonality, with various expressions and actions, particularly the depiction of actions and costumes.

In the Song and Yuan Dynasties, the religious figures gradually became secular, and the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eight constellations at the Zhengji of the Yuhuang temple reflect the characteristics of worldly vulgarization in the shaping of the characters. From the action of the figure, the 28su colored glaze art figure statues are essentially created by simulating the action characteristics of ordinary people. It's also self-evident that the characters' attire is that of everyday people. The colored glaze statues of the 28th temple have greatly broken the shackles of Taoist gods in the Tang Dynasty from the perspective of their costumes. They no longer wear thin clothing, wear a wide belt, and display their posture. Looking at the costumes of the 28th temple's colored glaze statues, it's clear that these colored glaze images are closer to real people and have a strong flavor of life. The Jin Dynasty lived in a time of multi-ethnic harmony. The clothing styles of the 28su glazed statues adopted realistic expression techniques under the influence of foreign culture, and the

clothing characteristics of the glazed statues were very distinct. In the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eight nights, we can see the figure of a "stomach pheasant" (picture). The god bird is lifted slightly with the left hand, and the clothing patterns on and below the left cuff are driven by this action. The cuff is a narrow sleeve with a smooth and natural drooping cuff edge to the knee; another representative image is the "winged fire snake" (picture). It is shirtless, with a ribbon wrapped around its arms and a green snake in front of its chest, and it appears to be both elegant and flexible. Except for a few warriors in armor or shirtless, the clothing of most of the other characters in the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eight nights is in line with the clothing of the people at the time. Their clothes are flat against their bodies, and they are plain and simple. The clothing patterns naturally fold and sag, and the density contrast between the lines has no effect on the presentation of the dynamic characteristics of the figure. Most of the colored glaze statues of the twenty-eight nights appear in the form of standing and stepping on auspicious clouds, and the clothes patterns naturally fold and sag.

Figure 1: Detail drawing of colored glaze ridge decoration of twenty-eight nights in Yuhuang temple (I)

Figure 2: Detail drawing of colored glaze ridge decoration of twenty-eight nights in Yuhuang temple (II)

6. Conclusion

Zezhou Yuhuang temple's colored glaze has a high level of scientific and technological content. Its unique colored glaze shape, on the other hand, makes it a highly ornamental work of art. The Yuhuang temple in Zezhou represents the religious buildings in southeastern Shanxi that not only pay attention to the artistry of colored glaze products, but also to the scientific of their production, achieving a high degree of unity between the two.

To begin with, the advancement of science and technology is a precondition for the growth of glazed art in Southeast Shanxi. Shanxi Province has a long history of producing colored glaze, and as a result, it has a wealth of experience with the long-term process of producing colored glaze. Despite the lack of a systematic scientific and technological theory of colored glaze production at the time, craftsmen have mastered the unique colored glaze production skills in practice and continue to absorb the methods of previous dynasties. The use of a material in the production of colored glaze evolved from the early use of a composite material. Colored glaze components have a wide range of characteristics because of the application of science and technology. [9] We can see a variety of colored glaze products at the Yuhuang temple in Zezhou, as well as a variety of forms and colors that reflect the power of science and technology. The glazed products of Zezhou Yuhuang

temple have become treasures carrying art under the guidance of science and technology. Furthermore, the incorporation of science and technology provides an important assurance for the circulation of glazed art in religious structures. The glazed products in Shanxi Province's southeast are a long way from the present, but the glazed products in their religious buildings can still exude artistic charm in terms of color and shape after thousands of years. The most important reason is that scientific and technological factors are supported and guaranteed. The drying speed, temperature, and humidity of the medium have all become important factors in the preservation of glazed products. The scientific composition proportion, advanced calcination technology, and scientific glazing method are used in the manufacturing process to ensure that the colored glaze in religious buildings in Southeast Shanxi keeps its bright color for a long time.

Second, the advancement of colored glaze art has effectively accelerated the advancement of science and technology. Shanxi Province, particularly the southeast region, has a high level of colored glaze production and artistic achievements. The colored glaze art environment also aided the advancement of local science and technology, particularly colored glaze manufacturing technology. The glazed products of Zezhou Yuhuang temple were highly skilled at the time of their construction and later restoration. It was a work of art in and of itself, in addition to serving the building's specific needs. This also caused the artisans to regard it as more than just an ordinary ornament in the production of glazed goods, but to refine and rigorously control the manufacturing process. In addition, as colored glaze art evolves, so does the technology used to make it. [10] The firing technology for colored glaze has been upgraded on a regular basis. We can feel the firing technology of colored glaze in different periods through the artistic shape, which also serves as a valuable reference for future generations to understand colored glaze production at that time.

Colored glaze products in religious buildings in southeastern Shanxi Province exhibit strong artistry as well as scientific and technological content, and the two have achieved a high degree of unity. Various colored glaze products, such as colored glaze components, reflect excellent scientific and technological technology. This scientific and technological content is conveyed through each work of art, so colored glaze art has not only become an important content of architectural culture, but has also given people the impression that China's long colored glaze culture has a far-reaching impact in both science and art.

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